

Qualitative Study on the Role of Technology in Entrepreneurship Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper focuses on entrepreneurship education as a mechanism for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. Issues discussed include nature of entrepreneur, entrepreneurship education technology innovations entrepreneurship development in Nigeria, the Goals of Entrepreneurship Education, its impacts, among others. The goals of sustainable development were also discussed, employment generation. This paper identified that although some strategies emphasize on entrepreneurship skills there is requirement for a comprehensive orientation of institutions with the sole aim of improving the entrepreneurship mentality of the youths. The aftermath of this is the generation of employment, increased output through innovations, efficient utilization of available resources and the facilitation in the transfer of technological advancement to mention a few have been identified as the contributions of Entrepreneurship to the development of a country. Based on these propositions as well other discourses a number of recommendations were suggested which includes; a call for stakeholders to recommit themselves towards development of entrepreneurship through the provision of adequate resources for teaching as well as well-equipped empowerment development centers. The paper emphasizes that based on the shared responsibilities for entrepreneurship development it can be employed as a viable tool for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: technology entrepreneurship education panacea for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Introduction

Technology entrepreneurship is basically a combination of two separate terms from two different disciplines, technology came from the discipline of innovation and entrepreneurship came from the business or commercial discipline. Hence it is an integration of technological and entrepreneurial domains. Technology entrepreneur is a person having specific knowledge and expertise vital for any entrepreneur in order to carry out technology centered entrepreneurial activities effectively and efficiently. Ogwedenge (2013) explained that collaborative research and development activities, producing innovative products, evolving new resources and their attributes which leads toward progression in scientific and technological expertise basically discriminates technology entrepreneurship from other entrepreneurship domains.

Today is the era where technology entrepreneurship has turned to be an important global portent. It is considered essential for progression, distinction and a vital tool to attain competitive benefit at organizational, local and national levels. It is becoming a central point of debate which involves initiating new business as well as rising of new startups, regional profitable progressions, opting out the most suitable stakeholders or investors to bring ideas to marketplaces and also educating and give training to managers, scientists, supervisors, Engineers, and technologists, Petti and Zhang, (2011). Practitioners and researchers claim that technology entrepreneurship is basically an investment in creating new ventures that accumulates and organizes particular individuals and divergent resources in order to catch value for the organization. This concept is more concerned with combined production grounded on a mutual vision of upcoming technological changes. Change in technology can be characterized in numerous ways. For that reason, it is essential to cultivate a shared opinion of any change in technology Shane and Venkataraman, (2013). This value creating concept is not only about to identify the technology or market

opportunities but basically about investing, exploiting that opportunity and generating high profit margins for the firm Shane, and Venkataraman (2013).

Conceptual Framework

Technology can be perceived as a product and as a process Yusuf, (2016). As a product, it is described as hardware, which is the device that conveys and supplies information to carry out and achieve a task. The hardware is the physical equipment used to store, project, transmit or retrieve information from the software. The software is the message carrier. As a process, it is observed as a method of applying resources to satisfy human wants and needs to widen human ability. It is the systematic process of solving problems by scientific means.

Concept of technology integration

Technology integration has been defined in numerous ways by different authors. For instance, Ntuli, and Kyei-Blankson (2013) refer to technology integration to the use of various digital and hardware tools to facilitate the process of teaching and learning in and outside the classroom. Dockstader (2017) believe that technology integration is using computers effectively and efficiently in the general content areas to allow students to learn how to apply computer skills in meaningful ways. Similarly, Kafyulilo (2015) maintains that technology integration is using software supported by the business world for real-world applications, so students learn to use computers flexibly, purposefully and creatively.

Belland, 2019: Newby, et al.,2016 and Ertmer, 2015: They believed that technology integration means using technology to make learning more efficient or effective as well as the use of technology to help students solve problems. Also, Redmann and Kotrlik (2018) saw technology integration as “making, modification, usage and knowledge of tools, machines, techniques, crafts, systems and methods of organization to solve a problem, improve a pre-existing solution to a problem, achieve a goal, handle an applied input or output relation or perform a specific function”. Technology integration has been regarded as the sustainable and persistent change in the social system of schools caused by the adoption of technology to help students construct knowledge, Gibson, (2011). Additionally, technology integration also has been defined in other ways, for example, technology integration is having the curriculum drive technology usage, not having technology drive the curriculum.

Concept of Entrepreneur

Entrepreneur is an entity which has the ability to find and act upon opportunities to translate inventions or technologies into products and services: "The entrepreneur is able to recognize the commercial potential of the invention and organize the capital, talent, and other resources that turn an invention into a commercially viable innovation." In this sense, the term "Entrepreneurship" also captures innovative activities on the part of established firms, in addition to similar activities on the part of new businesses. It is about bearing the skills needed to assume the risk of establishing a business. It is about developing the winning strategies and executing them with all vigor, persistence and passion needed to win any game". "Entrepreneurship is the process or capacity for organizing, operating and assuming risk for a business venture. It is dynamic risk-taking, creative and growth-oriented behavior which involves the use of various resources to create wealth, Ekanem (2015)"

Types of Entrepreneurs

1. Innovative Entrepreneurs: Innovators, who may invent, present new products, offer new methods of fabrication as well as discover new markets and opportunities.
2. Imitative entrepreneurs: usually cautious and skeptic in adopting any alteration in their business activities
3. Fabian Entrepreneurs: the second generation entrepreneur and usually slow in making decisions regarding changes in their business activities
4. Drone Entrepreneurs: reluctant to adopt new technologies, Inventions, opportunities even when these changes will reduce the cost of doing business, Ekanem (2015)

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education places emphases on youth development and also the desire and multiple competencies of individuals. It seeks to decrease the inherent risk attached with entrepreneurship while guiding the enterprise through its beginning phase to its maturity stage successfully, Ijsselstein (2010). It is structured to connect and adopt proficiencies, attributes and values required to recognize potential investment opportunities, structure and embark on new business ventures, Brown, (2018). Entrepreneurship education is an educational programme which focuses on impacting pupils on matters surrounding entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education is involved in the motivation, mentorship of youths and elders on approaches to become self-reliant in thinking, creating and operating a venture, (Gorman, Hanlon & King, 2016; Rasheed and Rasheed, 2013)

Characteristics of Entrepreneurial:

According to Gana, (2011) the Characteristics of Entrepreneurial are;

1. Self-confidence: This is can be characterized as one of the essential attributes an entrepreneur must possess. The entrepreneur must believe in his/her self and the project he/she intends to embark on. The entrepreneur should be able to see the obstacles or difficulties in achieving his/her goals as Challenges which must be faced squarely and conquered. The entrepreneurs must maintain a high level of emotional stability in the face of difficulties.
2. Risk taking: An entrepreneur must analyze and determine the risk inherent in the project he/she is embarking on and as such adopting strategies aimed at mitigating the potential exposure to these inherent risks. Gana (2011) the entrepreneur employs and focuses on his/her personal talent, capabilities, -competencies, technical know-how and values to navigate these inherent risks.
3. Job orientation: An entrepreneur is result-orientated. He or she sets difficult but achievable goals. The entrepreneur is dogged, tenacious and strong-minded. Drive and Energy: An entrepreneur shows high levels of drive and energy by putting a serious amount of physical and mental energy
4. Leadership: An entrepreneur encourages and guides individuals towards achieving set of goals and objectives.

Technological Innovation and Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria.

Entrepreneurship is about starting a new business based on a recognized business opportunity as well as operating and maintaining that business. The belief of some people is that entrepreneurship does not need to be taught and therefore, an entrepreneur is born to be so. It should however be noted that for one to be a successful entrepreneur, he/she needs to learn the skills Garba, et.al (2010). Entrepreneur training is designed to teach the skills and knowledge that is needed to know before embarking on a new business venture. This would enhance necessary identification and avoidance of many pitfalls awaiting the less well trained and vigilant contemporaries. The training may initially be perceived as a cost in terms money but it would eventually be appreciated. The study carried out by Taiwo, et al. (2012), on small scale food companies in Nigeria reported that one major sources of technological change in these companies is personnel (operators and craftsmen). The reasons adduced for these were simplicity of the innovation processes to the work force; accurate and adequate information about the system of production; and the involvement of the workforce in the initiation and implementation of any technological changes. Moreover, another research finding showed that the key information sources for manufacturing small and medium firms,, production and innovation are machinery suppliers, exhibition and trade fairs, client firms, publications, repair workshops (foundries, heat treatment shops and others), staff of other firms, social and professional associations, and consultancy firms within and outside the clusters, Oyeyinka-Oyelaran, (2013). Some researchers observe that increasing profit of organization is because of change in technology. Entrepreneur perspective innovation means creativity. "Innovation is a research area within the Marketing and Entrepreneurship Interface is a growing area of enquiry" Fialho, (2017).

Entrepreneurship opportunity identification and need to fulfilling innovation. Entrepreneurship and innovation is a key of economic growth, and there is strong relationship between entrepreneurial activity and economic development across the border. Entrepreneurship has also played a vital role in motivation. You can motivate entrepreneurship through culture, family and friend business. Another aspect of motivation is to motivate your employees by giving incentives, bonuses and increase salaries but according to entrepreneurship motivation is a deep meaning that to motivate your family and friend in the field of entrepreneurship you can give new and innovative idea to your friend to start new business and also running your family business with new creative ideas. We cannot understand entrepreneurship until and unless we understand the single who involve in motivation, Venkataraman, (2018).

Objective of Entrepreneurship Education

According to Paul (2015) the following are the objectives of Entrepreneurship

1. It offers an educational approach which is practical which enables and equips with the necessary skills to be self-reliant and self-employed.
2. It provides the youth and graduates with the necessary training that enables them to be Inventive and imaginative in recognizing investment prospects
3. It serves as a promoter of economic advancement and development.
4. It impacts positively on the rate of poverty.
5. It creates employment opportunities

Technology as a Tool for Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship education is essential to the creation of effective human capital in any country Eroh, (2017). The need for ICT as a tool in entrepreneurship education cannot be overemphasized. In this technology-driven age, everyone requires ICT competence to survive. Entrepreneurship educators are finding it very necessary to train and re-train their employees to establish, increase their knowledge of computers and other ICT facilities Adomi and Amic, (2016). This calls for early acquisition of ICT skills by students of entrepreneurship education.

The ability to use computers effectively has become an essential part of everyone's education. Skills such as book-keeping, clerical, and administrative work, stock-taking and so forth, now constitute a set of computerized practices that form the core information technology skills package: spreadsheets, word processors, and databases Adomi, (2015).

The demand for computer ICT literacy is increasing in Nigeria, because educators realize that computers and other ICT facilities can enhance entrepreneur education. On the other hand, educators have also realized that computers can be a threat to their job, and the only way to enhance job security is to become computer literate. With the high demand for computer literacy, the teaching and learning of these skills is concern among entrepreneurs' educators, Brakel, (2013). This is also true of other ICT components.

New instructional techniques that use ICTs provide a different modality of instruments. For the student, ICT use, allows for increased individualization of learning. In schools where new technologies are used, students have access to ICT tools that adjust to their attention span and provide valuable and immediate feedback for literacy enhancement, which is currently not fully implemented in the Nigerian school system Enuke and Emuka, (2014). ICT as a tool will prove beneficial in improving Nigeria's educational system and giving students a better entrepreneurship education.

Sustainable Development

The term "sustainable development" was initially coined in 1972 during the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment and later gained prominence by way of a report to the United Nations by the "World Commission on Environment and Development" which was chairperson by the Prime Minister of Norway "Gro-Harlem Brundtland" Was, Hüge, Verbruggen and Wright, (2011). Sustainable development entails that resources that are renewable should be employed in every possible situation and resources that are non-renewable should be used rarely in order to ensure their viability for the future generations to come Patil, (2014). Sustainable development entails the designing of a social and economic system that ensures the standards of education continues to improve, the rise in the real income maintained, the economic growth of the nation continues to improve as well as other aspect of life continues to increase Kyro, (2015). This cannot occur if the right type of education is not given to individuals. Sustainable development can be viewed in three dimensions namely; Economic, environmental and social United Nations, (2015).

Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria

Entrepreneurial development may be conceived as a programme of activities to enhance the knowledge, skills, behaviour and attitudes of individuals and groups to assume the role of entrepreneurs as well as efforts to remove all forms of barriers in the path of entrepreneurs. It is anchored on the firm belief that entrepreneurship involves a body of knowledge, skills and attitudes which can be learned and applied by most people who are sufficiently motivated. In contrast to the idea that entrepreneurs are born, entrepreneurship development recognizes that many individuals have latent potential to fit into the role of entrepreneurs. Such potentials can be actualized through training programme, Inegbenebor, (2016).

Entrepreneurship development assumes that through the process of learning, these characteristics or pattern can be acquired by anyone who is adequately motivated. Similarly, individuals can learn to deal with socio-cultural constraints and inhibitions prevalent in growing economies. Entrepreneurs can be trained also on how to establish and maintain effective relationship with financial institutions, suppliers, government agencies, and other critical institutions upon which they depend for information, guidance and inputs. It is possible to achieve all these through business counseling and by providing relevant information

Entrepreneurship

The education system with regards to the western educational system in Nigeria can be traced to the arrival of colonialism and scholars highlight the policy of education during that era was structured to serve the interest of the colonial masters with regards to supply of man-power for the administration of the Nigerian colony, Fabunmi, (2015), The policy as such was structured and targeted at graduating Nigerians who had the capacity and ability to read and write in order to become inspectors, interpreters and clerks while failing to equip them with the necessary entrepreneurial skills that enable them to identify business opportunities in order to establish their own ventures Aja, and Adali, (2013). Garba (2010) during this era the development of entrepreneurship was largely ignored particularly at the "micro-level" as the educational policy of colonial and the immediate post-colonial administrations focused on meeting the standards of "white collar jobs". Co-incidentally, obtaining these jobs was not the challenge then due to the fact the various opportunities for employment awaited yet to be graduated Nigerian students.

Over the years, the economy of the Nigerian state began to experience stagnation in growth and institutions and policies such as the "Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank" (NACB), "Nigerian Industrial Bank" (NIB) which can be labeled as the informal industrial sector was established Chete, and et al, (2015). A number of agencies were created by the government to assist the development of entrepreneurship such as the Nigerian Export British Journal of Education Vol.7, No.2, pp.58-72, February 2019 Nigerian Promotion Council (NEPC), National Directorate of Employment (NDE) Hassan,

(2013). However three notable educational policies worthy of analyzing are as follows; National Policy on Education (2014): This strategy places greater emphasis on the entrepreneurial education as subject number 34 trade and entrepreneurship subjects were introduced into the curriculum of secondary schools Adeyonu and Carim-Sanni, (2015). In addition, University of Nigeria, Nsukka now offers the following bakery, fishery, poultry, woodwork, garment making and auto workshop to mention but a few. From the above discussion it can be deduced that entrepreneurship has spread rapidly across universities and polytechnics in Nigeria and as such the Nigerian government should seriously pursue it by providing the much-needed facilities.

Challenges of Entrepreneurial Education in Nigeria and Possible Solutions.

As may be expected of this veritable tool for development, entrepreneurship in Nigeria is tainted with a plethora of problems. These problems, as highlighted in Inegbenebor (2012) and Kuratko (2003), are presented below together with the perceived solutions.

1. **Students' Orientation:** The place of passion is critical in cultivating and promoting entrepreneurial spirit in students. This follows that a passionate and committed student of entrepreneurship may end up taking the course as a career goal. Entrepreneurship, as it is today, is not taken by many as a vocational course of study in Nigeria, rather, wage earning is favored. This is a challenge to the field. But to stimulate students' interest in this line, a design of entrepreneurship education with significant promotional content as well as an enabling environment is needed for that purpose.
2. **Orientation of Schools Administration:** many schools' administrators are yet to appreciate the value and potential of entrepreneurship education in the development of the nation; hence, no real support is articulated by them. There is a need for the leadership of schools to re-orient themselves towards entrepreneurship development. Practical steps towards result-oriented entrepreneurship can only be achieved in schools only when school administrators themselves know and promote activities of entrepreneurial development. The National Universities Commission (NUC) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should go beyond prescribing the minimum academics standards with respect to entrepreneurship education to organizing seminars and workshops with the aim of enhancing the knowledge of school administrators in this area. The fundamental question of who to be the target in entrepreneurship education is another fascinating aspect of polytechnic and university administrators' orientation. Should entrepreneurship be an elective or a compulsory course? Should students be allowed to self-select themselves for entrepreneurship education? Whatever the answer to these questions may be, it is important that entrepreneurship is promoted heavily among young people. Special effort should be made to promote entrepreneurship education among students in science, engineering and agriculture where the potential for growing innovative, high growth firms is high, Inegbenebor, (2012).
3. **What to Teach:** What to teach depends on the overall aim that a given entrepreneurship education programme seeks to achieve. At the initial stage of entrepreneurship education, it was believed that the best that can be achieved by educators was to seek to change the perception of students by making them aware of the nature and scope of entrepreneurship, the characteristics and the role demands of entrepreneurs and the impact of social, economic and political environment on new ventures creation. Kuratko (2013), entrepreneurship education includes skill building in negotiation, leadership, new product development, creative thinking and exposure to technological innovation. Other areas considered to be important for entrepreneurial education are sources of venture capital, idea protection, characteristics of entrepreneurs, and challenges of each stage of venture development, and awareness of entrepreneurial career options. In relation to Nigeria, guidelines have been provided by the concerned regulating bodies. In spite of this, there is need for entrepreneurship teachers, educators and practitioners to brainstorm for the purpose of generating ideas about what to teach given the socioeconomic peculiarity of Nigeria. How to Teach: How to teach entrepreneurship addresses the issues of how best to stimulate students' interest in entrepreneurship, how best to transfer information, skill and attitudes relevant for successful venture creation and sustenance. Researchers have found widespread use of experiential learning in entrepreneurial education in most schools, Inegbenebor, (2016). Experiential learning is an effort to integrate real world experiences with conceptual learning. It involves various techniques as case analysis, business plans, consulting with practicing entrepreneurs as guest speakers, internship in entrepreneurially run businesses, student involvement in product development teams, simulation, field trips, use of video and films and so on. The major advantage of this method is that the students are actively involved in the learning process. Also, the lecture method which is suitable for providing information, explaining concepts and theories is widely used here necessary.
4. **Who is to Teach Entrepreneurship?:** Special training and experience are required for the purpose of teaching entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship teachers and facilitators should, as a matter of policy, be made to acquire the

requisite knowledge, skills and expertise for this purpose. Inegbenebor (2016) opined that one technique that can be used in improving the teaching of entrepreneurship is to encourage the educational institutions involved to share resources, knowledge and experience in this area through seminars, conferences and workshops. Also, business experts and practitioners should be invited as speakers to share their practical experiences in the course of managing their businesses or rendering consultancy services.

5. Teaching Facilities: Materials to aid the learning process of entrepreneurship in Nigerian institutions are not adequate, in the real sense of it. Entrepreneurship has, this day, remained largely the same as other subjects in terms of delivery. There should be hand-on teaching materials and equipment to aid learning process in the various institutions.
6. Capacity Building Centre: As alluded to in the point above, center for capacity building, where the intending entrepreneur is made to have hands-on experience are not adequate, if they ever exist in Nigeria. Incidentally, entrepreneurship is better appreciated in practical experience than in being theoretical. It is important, therefore, that the knowledge gathered in theory be backed by real life practical experiences in laboratories, workshops and business incubation sites, Okhakhu, and Adekunle, (2012).

Challenges Facing Entrepreneurship Education in Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Schools

Okoro (2014) have identified that there are both technological and pedagogical challenges with entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. Gidado and Akazeze (2014) describe the lack of teaching and learning equipment, such as computer accessories, internet facilities, and other technological resources to assist learners as major problems that face Business Education in Nigerian secondary schools. Therefore, for education properly serve as the motor for socio-economic growth and development, as well as for the actualization of entrepreneurship educational objectives in Nigeria, it is of paramount importance that secondary education and its systems function optimally in relation to its set standards of teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education (Ogundile, Bishop, Okagbue, Oggunniyi, & Olanrewaju, 2019; Akazeze, 2014). The authors stated that the issue of lack of technological teaching aids has generated an on-going argument which many has a link to the reason learners are not doing well as expected in their education.

Olutola and Olatoye, (2015) further stated that some secondary schools in Nigeria, equipment such as computers, projectors, software and internet are not available for proper utilization. New technologies in teaching and learning posed many challenges to the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria (Achugbue, 2011). Nigerian secondary schools would achieve the goals of Entrepreneurship Education if necessary modern technological teaching aids like computers, electric typewriters, projectors, internet facilities, among others, are adequately provided and used. Achugbue (2011), the reason many schools in Nigeria are lacking modern technological teaching aids, is that they do not give adequate priority and attention to the acquisition and utilization of new instructional technologies. As a result, the lack of such necessary facilities makes it difficult to teach and prepare Business Education students for the use of new technologies now and in the future world of work. The non-availability of needed materials resources for teaching and learning of Business Education has led to a lack of interest and motivation to study Business Education in Nigeria by many Olutola, and Olatoye,(2015).

Equally, pedagogical challenges have also been identified by Sithole and Lumadi (2012) as another issue in Business Education subjects. Furthermore, Omo-Ojugo and Ohiwerei (2018) reported inadequate textbooks, workbooks as well as the inaccessibility of digital technology and the internet to business educators to facilitate their teaching. The use of obsolete technologies is among the impediment of Business Education studies in Nigerian secondary schools. For example, manual typewriters are still largely in use and some available modern technologies are grossly inadequate Ugwuogo,(2013). Also, there is an under-utilization of computers, printers, other resources, and networking, and this might have resulted from the lack of skills to operate them Ugwuogo, (2013). Lack of training for the teachers and students to use the equipment has been identified as among the challenges that face Business Education in Nigeria.

According to Olutola and Olatoye (2015), the introduction of new technologies in the education system and the rapid nature of its expansion seem to overwhelm curriculum planners and other stakeholders in Nigerian secondary education. To ensure that Education is able to deal with global, technological and market changes, it is imperative to encourage Business Education teachers to adopt up-to-date interactive and participative teaching methodologies that are not only up-to-date but also internationally competitive (Nawaz & Gomes, 2014). Hence, as an important area of education in Nigerian, the goals of Business Education will be better achieved when combining its teaching and learning with technology. This is essential due to the present demand of today's office work. Therefore, the next section will look at technology policy in Nigeria.

Impact of Entrepreneurship in Developing Economy

There is no consensus on what classifies a developing country; however, a developing country can be described as a country that has not met its full potential with regards to technology, education, economy, security, Fialho and Van Bergeijk, (2017). Usually characterized with poverty, a developing country cannot meet the primary needs of its population. As such a

developing economy is an economy that is experiencing low levels of productivity, low income per capita, poor levels of technological advancement, poor infrastructures, low levels of life expectancy and insufficient health services, Inegbenebor and Igbinowanhia, (2010). These economies have challenges satisfactorily meeting the social, economic as well as other basic requirement of its population. Scholars have continued to highlight the important of entrepreneurship on the economy due to the process of entrepreneurship which involves the planning, operating and assumption of the risk of business venture that has implication on the surrounding such as:

1. Revenue Generation: scholars opine that the existence of entrepreneur in an economy will bring an increase in taxation that enables the government save, earn revenue as well provide basic Amenities for the populace.
2. Improvement in productivity through innovation: Analysts have defined innovation as a process where an entrepreneur converts available opportunities and ideas into solutions that are marketable and essential in improving production. Innovation remains an essential feature of entrepreneurship, Hassan, (2013). This is because through entrepreneurial efforts productivity in increased and it can contribute in moving Nigeria from its present state of being a consumption country to a production country.
3. Facilitation of technological transfer and adaptation: Prospects for developing and employing suitable technological approaches are given by entrepreneurs. This facilitates the absorption of all kinds of workers regardless of the fact that they are skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled Osano, and Koine, (2016).
4. Increase the utilization of resources: In most developing countries as a result of entrepreneurs certain resources that have been left to waste are harnessed by them for the purpose of production and profit. As such, entrepreneurs contribute in improving the domestic savings as well as the utilization of local resources, Ogedengbe et al., (2013).
5. Stimulation of growth: Due to the activities of entrepreneurs in large and small scale enterprises it encourages the diversification and sustenance of the economy. This diversification leads to the stimulation of economic growth while adjusting itself in dynamic nature of the global economy through the efficient and effective employment of raw materials and workforce, Hassan, (2013).

Problems of Entrepreneurship Education.

1. Absence of Mentorship: There is need to introduce a mentorship programme into the Training activities, so that young entrepreneurs can learn from successful businessmen.
2. Institutionalizing Business Training in skills acquisition programmes: Business training should be a core part of all vocational and skills acquisition programmes since most of the Graduate of these programmes are expected to end up in self-employment.
3. Short duration of Programmes: Most of the programmes are short of duration ranging from one week programmes to a few weeks or months. There should be enough time to incorporate practical elements.
4. Inadequate funding and capacity: Considering the magnitude of the youth employment Problem in Nigeria, and the number of potential beneficiaries there is need for increased Fundings in order to reach a larger number of youth annually.
5. Poor technology of the three key agencies, only the website of SMEDAN was functioning, and even the one has to register as a member to access information and this is a very different exercise.

Role of Entrepreneurship in the Economic Development of the Country.

1. Economic and Support Facilities Linkages: No business exists alone without contacting other organizations or enterprises for one thing or other. The various sectors of the economy seem to be interrelated in the areas of production, distribution and preservation. Entrepreneurs or business organizations provide the needed local manpower, technical knowledge and services needed to operate and maintain facilities for constant production.
2. Rural Saving Mobilization: the establishment of community banks is a policy to help to mobilize rural savings for economic uses. These savings help to boost economic activities in rural areas.
3. Utilization of Local Resources and Raw Materials: The establishment of small business has helped to mop up the local agricultural products because these enterprises make use of the products for local manufacturing and this help to check waste.
4. Generation of Employment Opportunities: All the small and medium scale business generates more employment opportunities than most big enterprises. Many people depend on their business for their employment and may employ others to assist them.
5. Stimulation of Indigenous Entrepreneurship Development: the experience and skill gained in small business help in the operation and management of big business.

Conclusion

Development through entrepreneurship has become the focus of all the nations around the world. This is better appreciated by the less-developed and developing countries of Africa, Asia and South America which need urgent transition to developed economy. However, economic development through entrepreneurship can well be sustained with a focus and investment in entrepreneurship education. It has become clear that entrepreneurship can be taught and learned. Business educators and professionals have evolved beyond the myth that 'entrepreneurs are born, not made.' Certainly, the future belongs to the nations who are willing to pay the required sacrifice today and for us in Nigeria, there is no better time to do this than now if the economic fortune of generations to come will not be further jeopardized! The identified challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria could be ameliorated with real commitment by all concerned government, educational institutions, students, and other agencies. It is hoped that, given this shared responsibility, entrepreneurship will take its place and be used as the viable vehicle for Nigerian economic growth and development.

Recommendations.

1. Stakeholders should to recommit themselves towards development of entrepreneurship through the provision of adequate resources for teaching as well as well-equipped empowerment development centers
2. Development through entrepreneurship should become the focus of all the nations.
3. Economic development should be through entrepreneurship with focus on investment in entrepreneurship education.
4. Business educators and professionals should evolved beyond the myth that 'entrepreneurs are born, not made.'
5. Entrepreneurship should take its place and be used as the viable vehicle for Nigerian economic growth and development.
6. There is need for increased Funding in order to reach a larger number of youth annually.

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